

Qualitative Analysis of DNA from Liquid Blood preserved in EDTA of Medico-Legal Cases

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Abstract— Blood is contemplated as the most prevailing and decisive evidence in medico-legal cases. Since it is a vital source of information for any case, therefore, its collection and preservation must be on top of the priority list. Many factors such as the type of anticoagulant used, the temperature at which it is stored, the analysis method, and the time gap between the collection of samples and its analysis could influence the evidence integrity. Any sort of negligence during the handling of the evidence can result in the loss of its integrity and ultimately lead to an injustice in the court of law. For routine practices in every lab, blood is collected in EDTA (Ethylene-di-aminetetraacetic acid) tubes for its preservation which can also be used for future reference in a particular case. This study was an attempt to explore any morphological changes /delicacy that directly affect the DNA quality of the preserved blood in EDTA. 10 Samples of liquid blood were collected in EDTA tubes at the two different conditions. The samples are divided into two batches with 5 samples in each batch. The first batch of liquid blood samples was stored under 4°C and the second batch was stored at room temperature. By following the organic extraction method, DNA was extracted. DNA of blood samples are set aside at the very same temperature and time. A comparative study of the quality of DNA is observed from the above 10 samples. The resultant will provide a clue as to whether any changes in the quality of DNA got affected by the EDTA and if it is so, then which factor is leading to those changes in the DNA quality.

Keywords— DNA profiling, Blood, Quantitative analysis, Evidence, EDTA

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Christopher Hitchens “What can be asserted without evidence can be dismissed without evidence”. To understand the above-mentioned topic, firstly, we need to understand the importance of forensic evidence and why they need to be preserved. Evidence in its widest sense incorporate all those things that influence an assertion’s truth. The term ‘Evidence’ has been acquired from the Latin word ‘evidere’ which means to ascertain or to prove. Rule no.1 of finding the evidence is that it must be pertinent to the investigation, otherwise, it would be of no use. Various types of evidence are attained from the scene of the crime like blood, hair, urine, semen, sweat, fingerprints, documents, tool marks, fibres, glass, gunshot residues, toxic substances, glass, etc. One of the most common forensic evidence is the biological evidence that is found in almost every case of crime. This type of evidence holds great importance in the field of forensic science due to the existence of DNA in the evidence [1] [2]. Diatoms, pollen, fungi and algae can be included in the examples of the evidence originated from plants. In addition to it, insects and microbes can be from animal origin. In this paper, the focus is on the biological evidence from humans, especially on blood evidence [5].

A. Basic Principles of DNA

DNA is a contemplated genetic blueprint that carries the information for transcription and translation inside the cell’s nucleus, known as Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) [3] [4]. The nucleotide unit of DNA has 3 parts: sugar, nucleobase and phosphate. Thymine (T), Guanine (G), Adenine (A) and Cytosine (C) are the 4 nucleobases. These 4 letters are accountable for all the diverse contrasts among all the living creatures. According to the rule of base pairing, discovered by Watson and Crick in 1953, hybridization can only take place between Adenine-thymine with 2 bonds of hydrogen, and cytosine-guanine with 3 bonds of hydrogen. Denaturation, a reversible process, takes place when these bonds break due to either an increase in temperature or by any treatment with chemicals like formamide [6]. The reverse nature of the denaturation process is known as renaturation, which takes place when the DNA cools down, the single strand of DNA will search for its compatible sequence and will rehybridize with it [7] [8].

Fig. 1 Polymorphic bands are scored as Present (1) or absent (2). Image 5(A) is clear, and the scoring would be easy but in image (B), the scoring would be difficult

B. Feasibility of Genetic Markers in Forensic Examination

Genetic markers are the DNA sequences with a well-known location on the chromosome. Usual genetic markers include minisatellites and SNPs. These are for identification of species or individuals. It is accepted that hereditarily pertinent data addresses under 10 % of the human genome. This trivial piece of the coding DNA has been exposed to transformative factors. Junk DNA is the other 90% of the genome, a term which is even more a misnomer since their capacities are yet unclear as opposed to futile. A piece of this non-coding DNA is involved in monotonous groupings [9] [10]. Exceptionally polymorphic spots in these non-coding areas are alluded to as smaller than usual or mini satellites described by rehashed squares of DNA [11].

C. Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism

Fundamentals of RFLP: It is an enzymatic method for separating and discerning the required DNA fragments. The whole procedure involves using restriction endonuclease enzymes which produce fragments of DNA and restriction probes to identify the required fragment. This is usually species-specific, highly locus-specific and co-dominant.

Perquisites for the use of RFLPs: Along with the requirement of high-quality DNA, it also needs to develop polymorphic probes. Besides the limited use of radioisotopes in specific and certified laboratories, it is a comparatively slow process.

- 1) *Random Amplification of Polymorphic DNA:* Fundamentals RAPD: In complex templates of DNA, random sequences get amplified by using short and single oligonucleotide primers. It means the size and length of the target genome and the primer will determine the fragment of DNA amplified by PCR. PCR will amplify the sample of DNA after adding primers [12]. Primers would attach to concealed sequences consequently and a comparative database would be acquired. The result reproducibility might cause difficulties, hence, not a reliable source for experiments as considered by many scientific journals.
- 2) *Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphism (AFLP):* Fundamentals of AFLP: It is based on the amplification of a subset of the DNA fragments from its complex mixture which is obtained later when restriction endonucleases work is done. It is the combination of RFLP and PCR methods [13]. The result is based on presence-absence polymorphisms rather than length polymorphism. AFLP is also used to ascertain the modest variation enclosed in a population.

Fig. 2 The height of each bar shows the likelihood of varieties being associated with divergent subgroups

- 3) *Simple Sequence Length Polymorphisms (SSLPs)*: These are frequently appearing sequences over different base lengths in DNA intergenic regions. The discrepancy in the SSLP lengths between 2 individuals can be useful to acknowledge the genetic differences in specific species [14] [15].
- 4) *Variable number tandem repeat (VNTR)*: These repeats are inherited for instance, parents and children repeats are matched in repeating patterns. A minisatellite is an arrangement of tandem repeats that vary from 9-100 base pairs [16]. It is found in regions of the euchromatin of chromosomes. They are not transcribed as satellite DNA sequences. A microsatellite is an arrangement of very short repeats, varying from 2-6 base pairs. These repeats differ among the population, and its individuals making them specifically useful.

Fig. 3 Illustrating the minisatellite and microsatellite of tandem repeat elements

D. Preservation of Blood Evidence

In general, the preservation of blood is done by using EDTA tubes because of their cost-effectiveness and ease of preparation. 0.1% or 1.5 mg/ml solution of EDTA can be used for the preservation of the blood sample. Cell shrinkage can take place if the quantity of EDTA rises more than 2mg/ml. EDTA (potassium) has anticoagulant properties which prevent the blood from coagulation [17]. Its anticoagulation property is based on preventing the aggregation of the platelets and other different reactions by chelating the calcium ions, which is required for blood coagulation. Conventionally, EDTA is the most common anticoagulant that is used to preserve the biological samples taken from the crime scene. Ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid contains 4 groups and 2 groups of carboxylic acid and amine group respectively in a 1:1 ratio. The lone pair of electrons on both amine groups chelates calcium ions along with other metal ions. Calcium becomes a necessity during the coagulation reaction

and its irreversible removal becomes a necessity to prevent the clotting of blood. Traditionally, 3 forms of EDTA are employed for anticoagulation: K2EDTA, NA2EDTA and K3EDTA. K2EDTA is the recommended choice in haematological tests by ICSH (International Council for Standardization in Haematology) [18] [19]. Depending upon the type of salt used, the pH of EDTA changes: as the quantity of sodium and potassium ions increases, the pH decreases. EDTA without any acid gives a pH of 2.5 ± 1.0 .

II. METHODOLOGY

10 blood samples were stored in EDTA for 6 months at 4°C . This was done to ascertain whether the delay of time would cause any change in the DNA result from the blood samples.

A. DNA extraction method

The organic extraction method is used to extract the DNA from the blood samples. The main objective behind the extraction of DNA from the cells is to get the DNA in a purified form for additional investigation such as in PCR and generating the profile of DNA [20].

Fig. 4 various reagents used in organic extraction

B. Organic Extraction Procedure

In this study, DNA was extracted from the 10 blood samples by employing the following procedure. Cell lysis buffer was employed to lyse the cell membrane. The nuclear membrane was still intact in the pellet. SDS (Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate) and Proteinase K were used in which the pellet nuclei were again suspended to lyse the nuclear membrane and for protein digestion. When the DNA gets released, it is kept in phenol-chloroform to detach the proteinaceous material. 95% ethanol in addition to

the salt is utilized for DNA precipitation in the ratio of 2:1. 70% ethanol was used to wash the DNA which is precipitated [20]. Later, it was dried under a vacuum and suspended again in the buffer of TE.

C. Quantification of DNA

Degradation and small aggregate of DNA are some of the factors that can hinder the process of DNA quantification. DNA quantification is essential to prevent the loss of samples of DNA extracted from the biological fluid. The best method of choice for the quantification of nucleic acid is Real-time PCR. RT-PCR is preferred over the conventional use of the PCR. Another advantage of utilizing RT PCR is that closed tubes are used to prevent contamination. Besides, the detection of the product can be done in each cycle of amplification. With the use of fluorescent dyes like HEX OR CY@3, quantification was done on 10 samples of blood stored in EDTA for 6 months at 4°C and at room temperature followed by STR analysis by employing Gene Mapper® [21]. During the exponential stage, DNA is quantified depending on the rate of deposition of ds-DNA by RT PCR with a very high resolution. The load of levels of DNA corresponds to the cycle threshold. During the exponential phase, the collection of data takes place [22].

Table 1. Steps of RT-PCR

Steps of PCR	Steps	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	Step 1	94-96°C	1-2 min/10-15 min
	Step 2	94-96°C	30 sec-1min
Primer Annealing	Step 3	50-70°C	30 sec-1 min
Extension	Step 4	72°C	1 Kb/min
	Step 5	Go to step 2 34 more times	
Final Extension	Step 6	72°C	10 min
Hold	Step 7	Hold at 16/4°C	

III.RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Some examinations are concentrated on the strength (capacity condition) of DNA. DNA and RNA tests from blood, particularly from WBC take longer time, and are the regular assessment focus for actual tests and additionally biomedical investigations. The accuracy of actual tests and accomplishments generally rely upon excellent DNA tests from blood. An anticoagulation mediator, EDTA is broadly used to prevent blood from agglutination by blocking additional enzymatic responses. There is no outright suggestion for the measure of the EDTA added to a sample of blood to guarantee agglutination measure with no negative effect. All DNA separation strategies were utilized as the convention in this investigation but didn't bring about EDTA defilement of the obtained DNA. The dashes of EDTA present in the blood test may be exclusively cleaned out after twofold ether-chloroform washing of processed blood by the lysis buffer. For that reason, the outcomes demonstrate no critical effect of EDTA level (up to 9 µg/µl blood) on the amount just as the nature of separated genomic DNA is in reasonable concurrence with hypothetical assumptions. The more elevated levels of EDTA (past 11 µg/µl blood) expanded the OD260 which in terms could be misdirecting by improving the OD260/OD280 proportion past 1.8-1.9, which is comprehensively acknowledged as a marker of top-notch DNA. To keep away from any uncertainty on the DNA extraction measure, the EDTA level at the beginning of the blood test should be kept under 9 µg/µl blood. Perhaps the main constituent of amplification of PCR is the Mg²⁺. Practically speaking, optimizing Mg²⁺ for a combination of templates is only sometimes done.

Table 2. This table shows the quantity of DNA from the first batch at 4°C

SI. No.	Blood Sample	DNA Quantity
1.	Blood sample no.1	62.50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
2.	Blood sample no. 2	65.32 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
3.	Blood sample no.3	60.52 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
4.	Blood sample no.4	78.34 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
5.	Blood sample no.5	52.50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Fig.5 Quantity of DNA from blood samples stored under room temperature

In this examination, we utilized EDTA-containing tubes to collect blood tests. Fresh blood is considered a luminous standard for clinical examples including fluid biopsies. In this way, the capacity span and capacity temperature, from blood assortment to extraction of DNA, are basic to excellent DNA tests. As a result of our study, although DNA is yet safe within 6 months when kept in entire blood, DNA amount somewhat diminishes inferable from the comparison between the temperature at which it is stored. In this manner, blood tests put away at 4°C yielded higher DNA than tests put away at – room temperature. Notwithstanding, the measures of DNA separated from the blood tests were adequate for most of the atomic science procedures. The 95% certainty breaking point of two measures of DNA showed that the measure of DNA after the capacity of blood at 4°C and room temperature didn't fundamentally contrast from one another. So, the yield of DNA is about something very similar at two temperatures.

Fig.6 Quantity of DNA from blood samples stored under room temperature

Table 3. This table shows the quantity of DNA from the first batch at 4°C

SI. No.	Blood Sample (Batch 2)	Quantity of DNA
1.	Blood sample no. 6	42.92µg/ml
2.	Blood sample no. 7	45.92µg/ml
3.	Blood sample no. 8	43.34µg/ml
4.	Blood sample no.9	46.52µg/ml
5.	Blood sample no. 10	35.13µg/ml

Table 4. Comparison between the average DNA quantities extracted from batches of blood samples

Quantity of DNA from batch 1	Quantity of DNA from batch 2
$\text{Average} = \frac{62.30+78.34+65.32+60.52+52.50}{5}$ $= 63.79\mu\text{g/ml}$	$\text{Average} = \frac{42.92+43.34+35.13+45.92+46.52}{5}$ $= 42.76\mu\text{g/ml}$

IV. CONCLUSION

Storage of samples of DNA is required to make a genomic DNA bank to decrease the future expense of examination. Effective long-span stockpiling relies upon the dependability of the DNA tests which thus relies upon conditions of storage. Blood can be conserved using various anticoagulants including citrate, Ethylene diamine tetraacetic corrosive (EDTA) or heparin. EDTA is the anticoagulant of optimal choice for blood for DNA extractions since it represses the activity of DNA and doesn't change the amount of DNA. Blood can be dispatched at optimum temperature, however, if the adjournment among assemblage and extraction is over three days, there will be some DNA degradation and the yield will be lower than that from new blood. Overall, it is suitable to carry the samples of blood at 4°C to keep away from contamination [20].

The utilization of fitting stockpiling conditions is basic to acquire DNA in adequate amounts. In this study, blood samples were conserved in EDTA over 6 months at 4°C & at room temperature. DNA was constrained by RT-PCR. Results showed that specific stockpiling conditions altogether affect the DNA extraction yield yet next to zero impact on DNA uprightness. Comparison from the two batches of blood stored at two different temperatures showed that the blood samples stored at 4°C gave a better quantity of DNA rather than the blood samples stored at room temperature. The fresh sample is considered a brilliant standard when managing clinical examples, including fluid biopsies.

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